

Classical Cluster Expansion and Generalized Statistical Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. March 23, 2020

The classical cluster expansion is often applied to Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) statistical mechanics for which there is a potential $\sum_{i<j} v(|r_i-r_j|)$ where r_i and r_j are vectors. In the case of generalized statistical mechanics, the "Maxwell-Boltzmann" weight $\exp(-(e-u)/T)$ is applied to $g(f(e))$ and not $f(e)$, the number of particles with energy e (although u and T still apply to constraints for f). For the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases $g=f/(1-f)$ and $g=f/(1+f)$ respectively. It seems that if a potential $\sum_{i<j} v(r_i-r_j)$ is added, the cluster expansion may be used for the normalization factor of g , but the "grand canonical partition function" can no longer be set equal to PV/kT . In this note, we try to examine some properties of $g(f(e))$ and a statistical mechanics which may be developed for g separate from the statistical mechanics of f , even in generalized statistical mechanics. g seems to be related to activity or more specifically to an overall measure of particles leaving the state e , incorporating restrictions and enhancements for rescattering into e . (For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case $g(f(e))=f(e)$.)

Interpretation of $g(e)$

In MB statistical mechanics, $f(e)$ is the probability for a particle to be in the energy state e . It is also the probability for a particle to scatter out of state e , i.e. one uses density arguments without any "special" factors inducing or preventing particles from reentering state e . For the generalized case, there are two functions to consider $f(e)$, the number of particles in state e , and $g(e)$ a measure of activity or the removal of particles from state e , including enhancements or restrictions. For the MB case:

$f(e) = \exp(-(e-u)/T)$ ((1)) where u , the chemical potential is part of a normalization constant

And

$g(f(e)) = \exp(-(e-u)/T)$ ((2))

(Note: Kaniadakis also uses the form ((2)), (1) which is applied to a Fokker-Planck equation. In previous notes, we use $g(f(e))$ only in a scattering balance: $g(f(e_1)) g(f(e_2)) = g(f(e_3)) g(f(e_3))$ ((3)).)

where u and T are still linked to constraints related to $f(e)$ namely:

$\sum_i f(e_i) = N$ ((3)) the number of particles and $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}} N = E_{\text{total}}$ ((4))

$g(e)$ results from the physics of the problem. If one "assigns" numbers to T and u , this implies a certain total energy and total number of particles in a system. $g(f(e))$ from (2) is unnormalized.

As a first step, it is good to get a better sense of $g(f(e))$. For fermions:

$$g(f(e)) = f / (1-f)$$

If $f \ll 1$, $g(f) = f$ and one has the MB case. It seems $g(f(e))$ measures the “density” probability for a particle to scatter out of e , namely $f(e)$ like in the MB case, but is then divided by $(1-f)$ the probability for state e to stop other particles from scattering into e . Thus, if one wants to measure the loss of particles from e , one must be concerned about scattering out of e , but also any reductions or enhancements related to bringing particles back into e . For large g , this means f is close to 1 and $1-f$ is close to 0. This leads to high relative values. For f small, as noted, one has MB scattering. Thus, one has to renormalize in order to obtain a new set of g probabilities related to “leaving” a basic state e . It is $g(f(e))$ which leads to the “independent” scattering scenario ((3)).

For bosons, the case is the opposite. $g = f/(1+f)$. For a large f , there is a strong probability to scatter out of e , but given the large number f of particles in e , there is the large, quantum mechanical enhancement for particles to scatter back into e . Thus, for large f , the g weight cannot become too large because particles are being induced to scatter back in.

Entropy Considerations

Given the generalized statistical mechanical condition ((2)), Kaniadakis introduces the entropy density S_d :

$$S_d = \int df \ln(g(f(e))) \text{ such that } \frac{d}{df} S_d + \frac{d}{df} f(-\frac{e-u}{T}) = 0 \quad ((4))$$

This returns condition ((2)). One may solve for $f(e)$ directly from ((2)) and ((2)) follows directly from a time reversal elastic scattering balance. ((4)), however, may be used in:

$$E - TS + uN \quad ((4b))$$

to obtain \ln of the grand partition function ((4b)) and so links scattering balance to traditional forms of statistical mechanics. It may be noted S_d is described strictly in terms of $f(e)$, e.g. for fermions $g(f) = f/(1-f)$ so $S_d = \int df \ln(f) - \ln(1-f)$ which is related to $f \ln(f) + (1-f) \ln(1-f)$ which (when integrated over phase space) yields an entropy expression identical to that given for fermions in statistical mechanics texts, but obtained using factorial considerations.

In this note, we wish to consider an activity entropy related directly to g and not to f . As noted above $g(f(e)) = \exp(-\frac{e-u}{T})$ where u and T are fixed by constraints related to $f(e)$, namely total particle number and the total energy in the system. By choosing numbers for u and T , one creates a system with a certain number of particles and total energy. $g(f(e))$ as it stands is unnormalized. It may be used in a Shannon's type entropy equation:

$-g \ln(g) + g \cdot (-e-u)/T$ ((5)) Taking d/dg and equating to 0 yields $g = C \exp(-(e-u)/T)$ where u and T are known and C is a normalization constant. One may argue the constraint used in this calculation seems a little forced, unless it may be given a clear physical interpretation. (Mathematically, it seems one may introduce different types of constraints, but one usually imposes a physically relevant one. A normalized g represents a new kind of probability (different from the number of particles with energy e). It is the probability to see $f(e)$ decrease.)

$$\int d \text{ phase space } g \cdot (-e-u)/T = \text{constant} \quad ((6))$$

Here $g(e)$ is the probability to have a net removal of a particle out of e so $e \cdot g(e)$ represents the net energy leaving state e during scattering (i.e. some $f(e)$'s scatter out, but other particles scatter in). (Note: In equilibrium, a certain number of e states "decay", but the same number are created in other locations. Thus, $g(e)$ seems to be a kind of local net decay rate.)

((6)) may be rewritten as:

$$1/Q \cdot d/db \int d \text{ phase space } \exp(-(e-u)b) \quad ((7a)) \quad \text{where } b=1/T \text{ and } Q \text{ is the normalization of } g.$$

T and u are given constants. Alternatively:

$$d/db \ln(Q) \text{ so } \ln(Q) \quad ((7))$$

plays the role of a kind of generalized free energy, but with a very different in physical interpretation from ((4b)) related to f , even though both are linked to generalized statistical mechanics. ((7)) is related to activity in the system. If one writes $Q = Q_a \exp(ub)$, then Q_a is the usual MB normalization.

Another important derivative to consider is: $d/dz \ln(Q)$ where $z = \exp(u/T)$. For $f(e)$ statistics, this gives $n(e) = f(e)$ i.e. the number of particles with energy e . In $g(e)$ statistics, it seems to yield:

$$z \cdot d/dz \ln(Q) = 1/Q \int d \text{ phase space } \exp(-e/b) = \int d \text{ phase space } g(e)/Q = 1 \quad ((8))$$

$g(e)/Q$ is the probability of a net scattering of a particle out of e including enhancements or restrictions of scattering back into e . Thus, it takes the place of $f(e)$, the number of particles with energy e .

For the MB case $\int e \cdot f(e)$ represents both the average energy in the system (if $f(e)$ is normalized to 1) and the average energy flowing out in scattering. For the generalized case, these are two separate values. $\int e \cdot f(e)$ represents the total energy in the system (with $f(e)$ normalized to N) and $\int e \cdot g(e)$ the energy flowing out in scattering. Thus, it is related to energy of net activity. This net activity, for fermions and bosons, is related to the number of particles in a state e , but also to enhancements and restrictions of scattering. (Note, that for a very high energy particle, $f(e)$ is low because there are so few of these particles, even though

the probability to scatter for a high energy particle should be high because it has a very high flux.)

Thus, it seems one may develop a “statistical mechanics” for g instead of f. The Kaniadakis approach (1), uses generalized statistical mechanics to develop entropy for f and consequently a grand canonical partition function for f. In this note, we suggest using Shannon’s entropy $-g \ln(g)$ for g and also try to obtain a partition function proportional to $\ln(Q)$ where Q is the normalization constant of g.

Classical Cluster Expansion

The classical cluster expansion is used in statistical mechanics (2) to calculate the partition function or normalization of the MB weight for the case of an interparticle potential: $\sum_{i<j} v(|r_i-r_j|)$ where r_i and r_j are vectors. The details of the calculation are given in (2) and it seems would apply to the statistical mechanics of $g(e)$ introduced above, because it is of an MB form. In particular ((2)) becomes:

$$g(e) = \exp(-1/T(e-u + \sum_{i<j} v(|r_i-r_j|))) \quad ((9)) \quad \text{Here } g(e) \text{ is unnormalized.}$$

The normalization of $g(e)$ may be obtained using the classical cluster approach given in (2) which essentially deals with $\sum_{i<j} v(|r_i-r_j|)$. A point we wish to make, however, is that in the calculation of the normalization of ((8)), (2) uses an approximation method, by introducing a “grand canonical partition function”. $g((e-u)/T)$ already contains a chemical potential u , fixed by constraints of $f(e)$, so to use a “grand partition function approximation”, one must introduce a second chemical potential u_1 . In particular, following (2), one uses:

$$1/V \ln(\text{grand partition function}) = 1/x^3 \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} b^i z_1^i \quad ((10)) \quad \text{where } z_1 = \exp(u_1/T)$$

Here the “g” grand partition function is a function of u, u_1, V and T where all but u_1 are known.

If one examines ((7a)) $Q = Q_a \exp(ub) = \int d \text{ phase space } \exp(-(e-u)b)$ $b=1/T$ and Q_a is the usual MB normalization factor. One may convert this into a grand canonical partition function using:

$$\text{Grand canonical for } g = \exp(ub) \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} z_1^i Q_a(i) \quad ((11))$$

$$\ln(g \text{ grand canonical partition function}) = ub + \ln(\text{grand partition function for MB})$$

This grand canonical partition function should be an approximation for Q and lead to the same normalization:

$$z_1 \frac{d}{dz_1} \ln(\text{grand canonical for } g) = [\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} i z_1^i Q_a(i)] / (\text{grand canonical for } g) = 1 \quad ((12))$$

If g is normalized to 1, ((12)) should allow for the fixing of u_1 . Normally in MB statistical mechanics, ((12)) is set to N , the number of particles in the system. In g statistical mechanics, u already fixes this. " u_1 " is used in an approximation method as using $\exp(u/T)^i Q(i)$ should produce a sharply peaked curve near $i=1$ for the grand canonical approach to be used.

Quantum Cluster Expansion

It may be noted there is also a quantum cluster expansion (2), but $g(f)$ and f already includes quantum considerations, so we are hesitant to use this.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $g(f(e))$ used in generalized statistical mechanics is the probability for a net escape from state e (i.e. corrected for enhancements or restrictions applied to scattering back into e). We also argue one may develop a "statistical mechanics" for $g(f(e))$ similar to that developed for $f(e)$ in MB, and even generalized statistical mechanics such as that for fermions, bosons and Kaniadakis entropy. Thus, we argue there is a partition function for $g(f(e))$. We also consider applying classical cluster theory to the statistics of $g(f(e))$ because it is Maxwell-Boltzmann like, although it applies to different physical ideas than those of $f(e)$. For example, $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)$ measures the energy in the system, while $\sum_i e_i g(e_i)$ measures the net average energy flowing out of a state e , i.e. the state e is corrected for enhancements or restrictions to flows back into to state e .

References

1. Kaniadakis, G. Nonlinear Kinematics Underlying Generalized Statistics (2018)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/cond-mat/0103467.pdf>
2. Huang, K. Statistical Mechanics (Wiley, 1987) page 218